

Islamophobia & Public Perceptions of Terrorism in the West.

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Abstract

This dissertation explores the relationship between Islamophobia and terrorism, focusing on the way Islamophobia shapes how Western societies view terrorism. The media, policy and gender have all played a role in creating the Muslim terrorist stereotype. This dissertation is a literature-based project. This dissertation is a narrative-based review and the findings are thematic. The researcher analysed scholarly articles published around this topic then identified relevant key themes. The review of literature revealed that the media contributes to the Muslim terrorist stereotype, as media representations often link Islam with terrorism. It revealed that terrorists have been constructed through policy, as policy often has an overwhelming focus on Muslim communities. It also revealed that islamophobia can be gendered and that Muslim women often face brutal anti-Muslim aggression due to their religious clothing identifying them as Muslim in public. This dissertation also highlighted the impact that the Muslim/terrorist construction has had on Muslims and identified that Muslims are often impacted in educational settings. This study has highlighted the need for a change in counterterrorist policy in England and Wales. Additionally, this study highlights a need for more positive representations of Islam in the Western media, to counteract the high levels of Islamophobia.

Contents Page

Acknowledgements	1
Abstract	2
Contents Page	3
Chapter 1: Introduction	5
1.1 Overview	5
1.2 Anti-Muslim Sentiment and the War on Terror.....	5
1.3 The Role of the Media	6
1.4 Linking Gender and Anti-Muslim Discrimination	6
1.5 Counter-terrorism Policy	7
1.6 Rationale	7
1.7 Research aim and objectives	7
1.8 Methodology	8
1.9 Summary	9
Chapter 2 Literature Review	10
2.1 Introduction.....	10
2.2 The Shift in Discourse Post 9/11.....	10
2.3 Islamophobia	11
2.4 The Way Muslims are Portrayed	12
2.5 The Role of Public Perception.....	13
2.6 The Role of Gender.....	14
2.7 Summary	14
Chapter 3: Why Does Society Falsely Believe That Muslim Groups are Overwhelmingly Responsible for Terrorism?	15
3.1 Overview	15
3.2 How the Media Contributes to the Construction of Muslims as Terrorists	15
3.3 Constructing Terrorists Through Policy	17
3.4 The Application of the Term Suspect Community to Muslims	19
3.5 Summary	20
Chapter 4: How Muslims Have Been Affected Since Being Stereotyped as Terrorists?	21

4.1 Overview	21
4.2 Anti-Muslim Aggression.....	21
4.3 The Impact of Muslims Being Branded as a Suspect Community.....	22
4.4 The Impact Policy has had on Muslim Individuals	23
4.5 How Gender has Impacted Anti-Muslim Aggression	24
4.6 The Ways in Which Muslim Men Have Been Othered.....	25
4.7 Summary	26
Chapter 5: Conclusion.....	27
5.1 The Relevance of This Research	27
5.2 Key Findings.....	27
5.3 The Impact of Islamophobia on Muslims.....	28
5.4 Concluding Argument.....	29
5.5 Strengths of the Research Project.....	29
5.6 Recommendations for Future Research	30
References	31

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Overview

This dissertation focuses on Islamophobia and how it links to terrorism. Islamophobia is a ‘contested’ term and lacks a clear definition. Professor Imran Awan and Dr Irene Zempi have recommended a working definition of Islamophobia that the United Nations should adopt. The definition is: “A fear, prejudice and hatred of Muslims or non-Muslim individuals that leads to provocation, hostility and intolerance by means of threatening, harassment, abuse, incitement and intimidation of Muslims and non-Muslims both in the online and offline world. Motivated by institutional, ideological, political and religious hostility that transcends into structural and cultural racism which targets the symbols and markers of being a Muslim.” (Awan & Zempi, 2020, p.2). Furthermore the UK established a new working group to provide the government with a working definition of Anti-Muslim Hatred/ Islamophobia that reflects a wide range of perspectives and priorities of British Muslims (Gov.uk 2025). Highlighting there is a need for a unified term to assist in combating the issue. The term terrorism lacks a clear-cut definition. Originally meaning state-sponsored violence, terrorism has deviated to induce fear and terror in order to control and dominate society, now known as political violence, directed towards the state (Greene, 2017, p. 412). This dissertation aims to depict how Islamophobia, which exists at vast levels in today’s society has framed the discussion of terrorism. The rise of Islamophobia in the West has raised concerns among scholars and policymakers (Ciftci, 2012, p. 306) it is also this that has created the motivation for this research project. This chapter will discuss the structured approach this dissertation will follow.

1.2 Anti-Muslim Sentiment and the War on Terror

As stated, there are high levels of Islamophobia in today’s society, motivating the need for this research project. Sirin et al. (2021) argues that anti-Arab and anti-Muslim sentiments have been around for a very long time but the terror attacks on 9/11 and the declaration of the war on terror took those sentiments to a much higher level in the USA and Europe than ever seen before (p.46). Demonstrating that 9/11 validated pre-existing feelings of Islamophobia. President Bush declared the ‘war on terror’ on September 20th, 2001. Bush stated the US would use every weapon necessary in war to defeat the global terror network (President Bush, 2001. Cited in Nguyen, 2019, p.27). The war on terror had a significant impact on Muslims all around the globe. In Britain, Qurashi (2018) argues that the ‘war on terror’ defines the era of Islamophobia for Muslims. However, the war on terror has also had a notable impact on non-Muslims. The ‘war on terror’ differs from a ‘stereotypical’ war (Durrani, 2020). Yet the

impact has been astronomical. According to a recent Gallup poll, Americans currently name “terrorism” as the most important US problem, superseding the formerly most important topic: “the economy” (Riffkin, 2015, cited in Sikorski, 2019, p. 92). Demonstrating how the war on terror has framed the American mind and created an axis of fear. This also emphasises the need for this research project. It is important to note that Islamophobia does not only demonstrate itself in the form of hate crimes or overt discrimination towards Muslims. A low percentage of Muslims in governmental positions shows clear indication of socioeconomic differences between Muslims and non-Muslims are secondary indicators of Islamophobia (Bleich, 2011).

1.3 The Role of the Media

This dissertation will critically evaluate the media’s role, and how it has framed the discussion and views of terrorism. Perry (2014) argues that the ‘war on terror’ marked an intensification of existing Islamophobia in the media (p. 76). The media shaped how society perceived 9/11 specifically. Just hours after the attacks, the media framed 9/11 as a story of good versus evil. ABC, CBS and NBC News specials mentioned the term ‘evil’ 16 times (Nacos et al. 2011, p. 169). This sparks the beginning of a dehumanisation process that depicts Muslims as villains or the enemy. In Britain, Muslims feel that part of the reason for their continued existence as unaccepted and often despised minority is based on the presence of the “evil demon”: the media (Abbas, 2004, p.30). Moore et al. (2008) found that 36 percent of news stories about British Muslims were discussing terrorism (cited in Jaspal & Cinnirella, 2010). The visual representation of Muslims in the media is also negative. Jackson (2010) argues that bin Laden is the most common representation of a Muslim since 9/11 in the media and this provides a visual association of Muslims with terrorism and fear (p. 12). This highlights how negative media representation shapes society’s mind to develop Islamophobic sentiments

1.4 Linking Gender and Anti-Muslim Discrimination

Anti-Muslim sentiments can have a fixation on gender (Naderi, 2018), often depicting Muslim women or Muslim men in a negative light relating to gender stereotypes. Post 9/11, the concept of gender differences within the war on terror created a hierarchy, placing ‘barbaric brown men’ and ‘oppressed brown women’ at the lowest rank (Khalid, 2011). For Muslim women in particular, this means that whilst women already face issues of gender discrimination, on top of this Muslim women face a combination of racial and gendered discrimination. Muslim women who choose to wear the hijab are at the centre of controversy (Olser & Hussain, 2005, p.142). As data collected by Tell MAMA identified, 80% of anti-Muslim attacks were towards visually identifiable Muslims, such as women wearing a hijab/niqab (cited in Allen et al. 2013). Muslim women are scrutinized as a result of the negative media

representations that Muslims face. Muñoz (2005) found that newspaper articles presented Muslim women mainly as: passive women, victims or veiled women (cited in Navarro, 2010. p,100). This dissertation aims to highlight the correlation between gender and anti-Muslim aggression.

1.5 Counter-terrorism Policy

Counter-terrorism policy was introduced long before 9/11 occurred. 9/11, however, shaped policy to have a biased focus on Muslim groups. Counter-terrorism policy in the UK aims to prevent terrorist acts and prevent individuals from being drawn into violent and non-violent extremism (Thomas, 2016. Cited in Gearon 2018). As this dissertation will argue in Chapter three, counter-terrorism policy has led to the creation of Muslims as a terrorist stereotype. Chapter four will discuss the impact that policy has had on Muslim individuals. As this dissertation will discuss, the counter-terrorism strategies in the UK have been criticised a number of times. This dissertation aims to demonstrate the link between counter-terrorism policy, Islamophobia and the way the public mind has been framed as a result of this. Aiming overall to demonstrate that Islamophobia has influenced the creation of policy, the way policy has been implemented and the way law enforcement reacts as a result of this. Additionally, how policy affects day-to-day settings such as schools and universities.

1.6 Rationale

This research project chose a literature-based approach instead of empirical research for a number of reasons. Firstly, empirical research is timely and would not have been feasible as this research project had a submission deadline. Secondly, for ethical reasons, to protect the researcher from any discrimination, such as from far-right groups that may protest against this research. Whilst there is an ever-growing body of literature on Islamophobia and terrorism, there is a gap in explicitly examining how Islamophobia is linked to the perception of terrorism. Existing literature often focuses on Islamophobia and terrorism as separate categories, this dissertation aims to demonstrate how the two concepts come together and how one affects another.

1.7 Research aim and objectives

This dissertation aims to demonstrate and discuss how Islamophobia shapes society's perception of terrorism. It aims to demonstrate how Islamophobia has contributed to the creation of the stereotype that Muslims are terrorists. This dissertation will focus on the following research questions and aims:

why society falsely believes that Muslim groups are overwhelmingly responsible for terrorism and what the impact has been since this stereotype has been constructed. This dissertation will focus on the extent to which post 9/11 counter-terrorism policy has had an overarching focus on Islamic terrorism and the impact that this has had on Muslim communities. Highlighting the complicated relationship between Muslim communities and law enforcement agencies. This dissertation focuses mainly on England and Wales but will reference the United States of America frequently because of the impact 9/11 had on Western politics and the dire impact it had on American Muslims. This dissertation will discuss how Islamophobia has framed the way society perceives terrorism in the post 9/11 era. Whilst this dissertation may discuss, reference, or look at documents pre 9/11 the main frame of the dissertation and focus is on the post 9/11 era.

1.8 Methodology

As a result of the literature review conducted in Chapter Two, the third chapter of this dissertation will examine the reasons why society believes that terrorists are always brown Muslims (Corbin, 2017, p.455). Additionally, the third chapter will discuss what the impact of the construction of this stereotype has been. When researching for this dissertation, the literature present demonstrated that there are multiple factors that influence the process of Muslims being viewed/branded as suspects. This assisted in creating the structure of this dissertation. It was crucial first to learn the reasons why society falsely believes that Muslim groups are overwhelmingly responsible for terrorism, before discussing what the impact of that construction is. This way, the reader grasps the context and then an understanding of the in-depth argument presented throughout the entirety of this dissertation. How is it that Islamophobia frames the way society views terrorism? When researching for this dissertation, there were many keywords identified which shaped how the research was conducted. For instance, when searching for articles the words 'Islamophobia', 'Muslim women', 'War on Terror' (important to note that whilst this dissertation does not touch on the War on Terror, it made it clear whether articles were pre or post 9/11 due to this keyword), 'Prevent', 'British Counter-Terrorism policy' and so on were often used in the search bar. Research for this dissertation was strategic, and it had a strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. For example, articles discussing counter-terrorism Policy in England and Wales would be in the inclusion criteria, but post 9/11 policy in a country such as France or Spain would be in the exclusion criteria as this dissertation has a focus on Islamophobia in England & Wales. Mostly, articles written before 2001 would be in the exclusion criteria it however, was sometimes necessary to look at articles from the pre 9/11 era. The limitations of this research are, it has highlighted much further research is required onto the topic and that this research project was too short to discover a complete conclusion.

1.9 Summary

This chapter discussed the motivation for this dissertation. This chapter discussed the media, the way gender impacts Islamophobia and the role of counter-terrorism policy. This chapter was the introduction to the dissertation as a whole and laid out the structure of this dissertation. The next chapter is a literature review of key literature based around this topic, then this dissertation will discuss the reasons why society falsely believes that Muslim groups are overwhelmingly responsible for terrorism, then it will discuss what the impact of that construction is and finally this dissertation will have an overall conclusion.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This literature review will explore various aspects of terrorism, including its formation and the factors that shape our understanding of it. It will examine the influence of media on public perceptions of terrorism, the role of Islamophobia in shaping these views and how policy has addressed terrorism and contributed to its public perception. Additionally, it will investigate the role of gender, particularly in relation to female clothing within the Muslim community and its connection to terrorism. There is considerable research on this topic, with Nazia (2018) questioning if terrorism is committed by Muslims, stating it is in the name of Islam, is there something within the Islamic faith that drives some of its followers to engage in acts of extremist violence? (p.27). As there is a vast amount of literature on this topic, this literature review will focus on key authors such as Arun Kundnani and Chris Allen. Furthermore, focusing on key issues and topics to give an in-depth and detailed argument.

2.2 The Shift in Discourse Post 9/11

The perception and discourse surrounding terrorism underwent a significant shift following the September 11, 2001, attacks on the Twin Towers in New York. As this dissertation will argue, there was a shift in mindset after 9/11, with a growing focus on Muslim individuals and Islamic terrorism. In 2002, President Bush announced that America's three greatest threats Iran, Iraq and North Korea constitute an 'axis of evil' armed to threaten the peace of the world (Ryan, 2003, p. 55). Breen-Smyth (2013) argues the public mind formed a distinguished "other", motivated by these declarations from the Bush administration. Furthermore, Kundnani (2014) states that "the default assumption remains that the term 'terrorist' is reserved for acts of political violence carried out by Muslims" (P16). This dissertation will look into the concept that when discussing terrorism and terrorist acts, there is an overarching focus on Muslims and Islamic terrorism.

It can be argued that the term and concept of terrorism are now commonly associated with Islamic terrorism. In the aftermath of 9/11, Muslims have faced heightened scrutiny and surveillance, living under the constant fear of being accused of involvement in suspicious activities. As a result, Muslims have been stereotyped as the default suspects for terrorism. Breen-Smyth (2013) emphasizes that "suspects" are often identified by cultural or racial markers, not personal characteristics, leading to uninvited interventions in their daily lives. One key theme that comes up when researching this topic is Islamophobia. This dissertation will argue that there is a correlation between the prevalence of

Islamophobic attitudes in society and the way Muslim individuals are viewed and perceived. Islamophobia as a concept is widely discussed and debated, the term 'Islamophobia', first originating in the late 1980s refers to dread or hatred of Islam- and, therefore, to fear or dislike of all or most Muslims (Runnymede Trust 1997, p.1). Although the term 'Islamophobia' is widely used, it is not officially recognised as racism (Massoumi et al., 2017). Islamophobia is committed by non-Muslims and directed towards Muslims. Islamophobia is often discussed in relation to events such as 9/11 and acts of Islamic terrorism. Allen (2010) notes that, "Islamophobia existed as much on the 10 September 2001 as indeed it did on the 12 September 2001" (p.14). This argument pushes that Islamophobia is not a new or 'modern' concept but a concept that has been around for many decades. There is an overarching argument in literature that 9/11 acted as a catalyst for Islamophobia, however, as this dissertation will argue in more detail, 9/11 did not create Islamophobia. It simply gave individuals a platform to express their anti-Islamic feelings and opinions. Allen (2010) argues that if Islamophobia is viewed as a result of 9/11, then individuals make basic assumptions: if terrorism stops, so will Islamophobia.

2.3 Islamophobia

The term "Islamophobia" itself is open to debate, as it encompasses a wide range of scenarios in which Muslims face unjust bias. This includes hateful attacks on social media, physical violence directed at the Islamic faith, and assaults on institutions such as mosques (Lean, 2019). Kundnani (2017) argues that when scholars discuss Islamophobia, they do so in two approaches: 'personal' and 'structural'. When discussing the 'personal approach', Islamophobia can be understood as a part of individual psychology. This fear is often linked to events such as 9/11, where the association of Muslims with terrorism became deeply entrenched, and it is commonly expressed through stereotyping (Byers and Jones, 2007; Croucher et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2009. Cited in Kundnani, 2017, p.36).

Kundnani (2017) carries on this argument by discussing the 'structural approach', stating that it is rooted in social process, it can be connected to or caused by government policies, and it may be tied to broader questions of political ideology and systems of power (p, 36). Islamophobia can affect all Muslims, including students. The Federation of Student Islamic Societies (FOSIS) conducted a survey into the feelings of Muslim students in universities in the UK, the results showed that almost half of Muslim students have experienced Islamophobia, mostly defined as direct or verbal, with a quarter of the incidents occurring on a university campus (Coughlan, BBC report 2005). The literature present shows that more often than not, society as a whole is led to believe terrorism is only committed by Muslims. This dissertation will argue that this is due to the high prevalence of Islamophobia in society. Muslims have been stereotyped and are now at the forefront of counter-terrorism legislation. One key

theme highlighted is the role of the media. Literature has shown that the main-stream media tends to portray Muslims in a negative light, often only discussing Muslims in relation to violence, extremism, or terrorism (Jackson, 2007). Additionally, the mainstream media tends to report more on acts of terrorism that are committed by Muslim individuals (Nazia, 2018), with acts of terrorism committed by white individuals gaining significantly less media coverage. As a result of bias towards Muslims within the main-stream media, Islamophobia can be seen seeping into everyday life. “The most common nouns used in relation to British Muslims are ‘terrorist’, ‘extremist’, ‘Islamist’, ‘suicide bomber’ and ‘militant’ (Moore et al. 2008, cited in Mythen et al. 2009, p. 742). Emphasising the normalisation of Islamophobia and how common it truly is. Richardson (2001) found Muslim voices substantially excluded from British domestic reporting of Islam” (Husband & Alam, 2011, p.78). These two points link together: when discussing British Muslims, negative connotations are used, and when discussing Islam in the media, Muslim voices are silenced. This dissertation will argue that it is this, the regularity of Islamophobia that leads us to link the term terrorism to Muslims and Islamic terrorism.

2.4 The Way Muslims are Portrayed

In addition to Islamic terrorism, acts by the Far-right groups and individuals have increased. Collins (2021) stated that Far Right Terrorism activity in the UK targets local Muslim communities and that between 2009 and 2018, 33 out of 59 cases of Far-Right Terrorism were aimed at ethnic Muslims or Islamic institutions. Showing over half of these were discriminating against Muslims. There are policies in place to counter violent extremism. Prevent is a key strand of the UK government’s wider counter-terrorism strategy known as CONTEST that was introduced in 2006 by the Labour government following the London bombings of July 2005. The policy focuses on dealing with so-called ‘extremist ideology’ propagated by groups and individuals loosely defined as ‘Islamic extremists’ (Sian, 2017 p.3). Prevent has faced much scrutiny from academics with Tufail and Poynting (2023) arguing that it is racially biased and Islamophobic due to its overarching focus on the Muslim community. Surveillance is one of the core principles in the Prevent discourse. Drawing in the civil society and public sector bodies to spy on and control the Muslim body (Sian, 2017, p6). Furthermore, Aked (2017) argues that Prevent is not only a product of Islamophobia but also contributes to Islamophobia. Meaning that Prevent is the way it is because of the deep-rooted Islamophobia in society, but also that, Islamophobia is present in society because of the Prevent policy. The aim of Prevent is to have formal state intervention at an early stage with individuals and groups to challenge violent extremism. Additionally, the government aims to intervene when an individual begins to engage with terrorist literature and terrorist organisations. Akbar (2013) argues that the radicalisation discourse has an excessive focus on Muslims and Islam in spite of data that highlights the terrorist threat from Muslims is rare to minimal including in comparison

to violence from white-supremacist and far right groups (p.811). As previously mentioned, there is a lack of focus on terrorist organisations that are not Islamic.

2.5 The Role of Public Perception

Mavelli (2012) argues that Muslims were successfully targeted due to a process whereby 'terror' became translated into 'Islam'. However, Volpp (2020) argues why she believes Muslims have been branded as terrorists. She states that 9/11 "facilitated the consolidation of a new identity category that groups together persons who appear "Middle Eastern, Arab or Muslim" (p.19). She states that "this consolidation reflects a racialization wherein members of this group are identified as terrorists and are disidentified as citizens" (Volpp, 2020, p.19). Both arguments result in the same conclusion: Muslims and terrorists are often merged together in vocabulary. Before the London bombings of July 2005, the most serious terrorist attack in London was committed in 1999 by a white Supremacist David Copeland. Copeland conducted 3 attacks over a period of 13 days and targeted a well-known gay venue, which resulted in the death of 3 and injured over 100 (Thomas, 2012). This example identifies that terrorism is not only committed by Muslims but highlights that the media has an overrepresentation of Islamic terrorism. There is a mass misconception that the religion of Islam condones terrorism: this statement is false. The killing of women, children, unarmed civilians, religious leaders, and non-combatants is strictly forbidden in Islam, even during times of conflict (Fidow et al. 2021, p.20). When discussing Al Qaeda specifically, they did not always target civilians, however in 2002 Bin Laden wrote a "Letter to the American People", where he stated he justified killing American citizens due to the fact America is a democracy- he states that "the American people are the ones who choose their government by way of their own free will; a choice which stems from their agreement to its policies. Thus, the American people are complicit in America's policies in the Muslim world" (Byman, 2015, p.28). Osama Bin Laden is one individual and whilst his opinions or views do not apply to the entirety of Islam, Reports based on several assessments by security and intelligence officers post 7/7 found that the war on Iraq did contribute to the radicalisation of the July 7th bombers and can be said to be a likely cause of radicalisation amongst British Muslims (Bux 2007). This highlights the link between foreign policy, specifically in the Middle East, and acts of Islamic terrorism. When discussing the nature and causes of the Islamic terrorist threat, the mainstream media tends to have an overarching focus on mosques and their role (Thomas, 2012). This, however, is just another demonstration of how Islamophobia can seep into the mainstream media. Thomas (2012) argues that many Islamists who had been drawn towards violent extremism had already cut ties with local mosques.

2.6 The Role of Gender

Gender is a key theme relating to this topic. As Abu-Raiva et al. (2011) discovered, Muslim women expressed that surveillance introduced post 9/11 caused a significant amount of stress in their lives (cited in Selod, S. 2018). Muslims were exposed to violence since the initial declaration of the war on terror, Lori Peek (2010) interviewed Muslim women and found that “immediately after the Boston Marathon bombing, a Muslim woman who wears the hijab was physically attacked by a man in Boston” (cited in Selod, 2018 p.101). The clothing attire of Muslim women has gained much attention and scrutiny in the period post 9/11. Aliamohed-Wilson (2017) argues that the headscarf signifies difference and poses a perceived threat to society. Aliamohed- Wilson (2017) linked the importance of gender to American politics and the media, stating that when media outlets report on Muslim women’s experience of violence, they focus on Muslim men within Middle Eastern countries as the perpetrators. Cainkar (2009) found that Arab and Muslim women experience twice the rate of “hate encounters” compared to their male counterparts (cited in Alimahomed-Wilson, 2017, p.77). Showing the role that gender plays.

2.7 Summary

The literature present highlighted that Muslims and the religion of Islam are facing unfair scrutiny and are at the forefront of counterterrorism policies. A number of authors argue that it is Islamophobia that causes Muslims to be treated unfairly and branded as “suspects”, “others”, “terrorists”. Secondly, the literature has demonstrated that the mainstream media plays a role in the representation of Muslims and Islam. It has been shown that Muslims are persistently discussed in a negative light in the media. Thirdly, it has highlighted that governmental policies, with an emphasis on the UK governments counterterrorism strategy Prevent, have a great focus on Muslims and that these policies can in fact end up pushing individuals to terrorism instead of preventing it. Further research is needed on the correlation between the prevalence of Islamophobia in society and how it leads Muslims to be branded as terrorists, research is also needed on the impact this has on Muslims. The literature presents links to the research conducted in this dissertation; this dissertation aims to demonstrate how Islamophobia frames the way society views terrorism. This dissertation aims to fill a gap in the research that has been identified. Islamophobia has such a strong presence in society, presenting itself in policy, the mainstream media, etc that it has framed the way society views terrorism as a whole.

Chapter 3: Why Does Society Falsely Believe That Muslim Groups are Overwhelmingly Responsible for Terrorism?

3.1 Overview

Why is it that society falsely believes that Muslim groups are overwhelmingly responsible for terrorism? Louati discusses the term “Islamodiversion”, stating that this is when there is an excessive fear of Muslim terrorists; the fear becomes a preoccupation distracting society from present everyday threats. Louati argues that Islamophobia has made the public obsessed with the threat posed by Muslims (cited in Nazia, 2018, p.28). This chapter will discuss how Islamophobia has gained such a strong presence in society and how this has contributed to the development of these false beliefs. This chapter will discuss the role of the media, focussing on how Muslims are portrayed in a predominantly negative light within the mainstream media. It will discuss the role of gender- how Muslim women have been painted as oppressed and in need of saving, and how Muslim men have been “othered,” categorised as a dangerous group and as a result of this, overly policed. It will also look at the lack of media discussion about anti-Islamic terrorist groups. It will examine policy in England and Wales, focusing particularly on counterterrorism strategies and how it has been designed to address Islamic terrorism and track the movements of Islamic groups. Finally, this chapter will discuss the concept of the suspect community and how this has been applied to Muslims.

3.2 How the Media Contributes to the Construction of Muslims as Terrorists

The media plays a significant role in constructing the Muslim community as terrorists. Negative representations of Muslims in the media are not a post-9/11 phenomenon (Moore et al. 2008, cited in Richardson, 2010). This chapter, however, will focus on the way in which Muslims have been shaped as terrorists post 9/11. Since September 11, media coverage of Muslims and Islam has increased dramatically (Poole, 2006; Whittaker, 2002. Cited in Meyer, 2012, p184). Whittaker (2002) researched specific news outlets and found that in *The Sun* newspaper, the number of articles containing the word ‘Muslim’ increased by 68% between 2000/2001 and 2001/2002 (cited in Meyer, 2012, p.184). Although

it is clear that media attention circulating Muslims increased post-9/11, it is important to note how the mainstream media focuses on portraying Muslims.

The mainstream media can have an overarching focus on portraying Muslim women as oppressed. Often, the Western media tends to depict Muslim women as needing to be saved, with figures like Laura Bush and Cherie Blair taking it upon themselves to speak out on behalf of the women of the Muslim world (Morey & Yaqin, 2011). Muslim women tend to be belittled and used as a pawn for anti-Muslim propaganda, often only painted as abuse victims. The American media outlets tend to focus on the violence Muslim women experience at the hands of Muslim men within Middle Eastern countries (Alimahomed, 2017, p.76). Whilst this is an important topic to bring light to, when discussing violence that Muslim women face, the violence they face at the hands of non-Muslims should also be discussed. Furthermore, Muslim women are often associated with female genital mutilation, 'honour' killings and having a lack of rights (Alsultany, 2012). Overall, Muslim women are exploited to support anti-Islamic views. With regards to the US, there is a pro-feminist focus on how women in Afghanistan are deprived of education and employment and are forced to wear the burqa, there is no mention of how the war conditions, militarization, and starvation harm Muslim women (Alsultany, 2012, p80). This demonstrates how the US has attempted to justify its military presence in the Middle East by using the media to depict Muslim women as oppressed.

A 2008 Gallup poll of fifty thousand Muslims from thirty-five different countries has shown that the majority of Muslim women do not see Islam as an obstacle to their progress but as a crucial component (Who Speaks for Islam? What a Billion Muslims Really Think, cited in Alsultany 2012, p.81). The violence Muslim women face because of anti-Islamic aggression will be discussed in more depth in chapter 4. Norton (2015) states that whilst there are hundreds of terrorist attacks that occur in Europe each year, it is the ones carried out by Muslims that receive media attention, headlines at every news outlet (cited in Sultan, 2016, p.3). Lewis (2003) pointed out that Muslims are offended when media outlets label terrorist's actions "Islamic" yet do not brand Irish or Basque terrorists as "Christian". This point is very important, it emphasises a form of bias within the media, publishing terrorist attacks stating the sole cause is Islamic reasons, places unfair negative attention on Islam and Muslims, this however does not seem to occur with far-right extremism, or acts of terrorism committed in the name of a different religion.

Vidgen and Yasseri (2020) conducted a study on detecting weak and strong Islamophobic hate speech on social media. They defined strong Islamophobia on social media as "Content which explicitly expresses negativity against Muslims." and weak Islamophobia on social media was defined as "Content

which implicitly expresses negativity against Muslims". (p.69). Some examples of strong Islamophobic tweets they identified were; 'Muslim men groom and rape children', 'Muslim mother's support FGM' and 'Typical, another bloody Muslim just blew himself up'. (p.69). Vidgen and Yasseri (2020) argue that weak Islamophobia can emphasise perceived differences between Muslims and other members of society (p.69). This demonstrates that Islamophobia is present on social media. Paterson et al. (2018) conducted a survey whereby they asked 129 Muslim participants about their experiences of online hate and found that around 80 percent had experienced online hate (p.22). We can see that this has very negative consequences. Eckert et al. (2018) argue that encountering Islamophobia online leads to communities experiencing high stress levels as it is more relentless (cited in Wiedlitzka et al., 2023, p90).

3.3 Constructing Terrorists Through Policy

Policy reinforces the notion that all Muslims are terrorists or associated with terrorists. Post 9/11 counterterrorism policy was created, designed, and tailored to counter Islamic terrorism; it was put in place with the aim to survey Muslim communities. In 2006, the government of the United Kingdom stated, "The Government assesses that the current threat in the UK from Islamist terrorism is serious and sustained" (White Paper 2006, cited in Husband & Alam, 2013, p.246). This clearly shows that after the 7/7 London Transport bombings the government had a key focus on countering Islamic extremism. The creation of 'Prevent' specifically fortifies that the UK government was going to treat Muslims differently through policy. Prevent has been criticised a great deal and in 2018 the UN Special Rapporteur for Human Rights said that Prevent was "inherently flawed", raised "very serious human rights concerns" and found there was no evidence Prevent actually prevents extremism" (MEND, 2018, cited in Tufail & Poynting 2023 p.193). As shown, Prevent has been accused of being ineffective and biased. Copsy et al. (2013) add to this by arguing that under the notion of prevent, policing tends to construct Muslim communities as 'suspect populations'. This reinforced the impression that Muslims are viewed by the authorities as potential terrorists or terrorist sympathisers (p.8).

As this dissertation argues, policy is a key factor that solidifies Islamophobic views in society. Policies are official government documents; they hold value, and the way policy is written and produced can influence an individual's thought. For instance, bias policy can influence bias mindsets. In chapter four this dissertation will discuss the way in which Prevent has led to Muslims, often Muslim students, being stereotyped and scrutinised within academic environments. Abbas (2019) argues that Prevent contributes to Islamophobia as a consequence and a driver of hate, intolerance, and violent extremism (p.397). This argument is crucial. It identifies that Prevent is a product of and a contributor towards

Islamophobia, as highlighted earlier in this dissertation by Aked (2017). Prevent is biased in the way it is hyper-focused on Muslim communities. As Thomas (2010) argues, Prevent labels an entire community as susceptible to terrorist involvement (p.446) when in fact it is a minority of members of the Muslim community that hold what would be classed as extremist views. Adding to this, Humera Khan, a prominent Muslim campaigner, argued, 'The Prevent policy has further demonised the Muslim community, as if we are all responsible for terrorism' (cited in Toole et al. 2012, p.377). Whilst this dissertation argues that Prevent is inherently biased and contributes to societal Islamophobic attitudes. It is important to note that it was created for a purpose and as a reaction to the 7/7 London Transport bombings. It, however, is outdated and needs to be re-evaluated.

Prevent is not the only form of policy or state activity implemented that has shown all Muslims are viewed as suspicious. Project Champion was a police surveillance operation which involved the installation of 216 overt and covert CCTV and ANPR cameras in two areas of Muslim settlement, this led to a 'surveillance ring' around these areas (O'Toole et al., p.171). Implementing hidden cameras is a complete breach of civil liberties. The Terrorism and Allied Matters fund had paid for the cameras. The Muslim community were viewed as potentially vulnerable to extremism (HM Government, 2006, cited in Awan, 2012, p.25). The surveillance highlights the deep-rooted Islamophobia within modern society, hiding cameras, viewing an entire community as suspicious and surveying them because a tiny minority may hold extremist views. Husband & Alam (2013) argue that in the last decade both community cohesion and counter-terrorism policies colluded in unambiguously framing British Muslim communities as distinctly salient, different, and therefore as a threat (p.251).

As well as Prevent there was something similar known as Community Cohesion. It was targeted at Muslim communities and required local authorities to engage with these communities attempting to counter the risk and reduce the susceptibility to radicalisation (Husband & Alam, 2013). Community cohesion was implemented locally following disturbances in Bradford, Burnley, and Oldham (Lewis & Craig, 2014). Community cohesion was then made central in national and local government policies responding to ethnic diversity and conflict (Thomas, 2007, cited in Lewis & Craig 2014, p.23). Community cohesion, like Prevent was met with much backlash. Ahmed (2019) argues that policies such as Prevent and community cohesion predominantly focus on British Muslims and contribute to the injustices and grievances experienced by British Muslims.

3.4 The Application of the Term Suspect Community to Muslims

As discussed, policy has had a great impact in shaping the way that the Muslim community is viewed. Muslims have been categorised as suspects. Pantazis and Pemberton (2009) applied the term “suspect community, which originally had connotations with the Irish in Britain. Pantazis and Pemberton applied this term to Muslims in Britain, defining it as a sub-group of the population that is singled out for state attention as being ‘problematic’ (cited in Breen-Smyth, 2014, p.224). Walklate (2014) argues that there has been a recent resurgence in the academic interest of the ‘suspect community’ concept due to ongoing media attention on the discourse of terrorism. Linking back to Prevent, Pantazis and Pemberton (2009) argue that the legislative framework that had been developed in response to the new threat of terrorism identifies Muslims as the predominant target of the state’s attention (p.649). It can be argued there is a link between policy and the branding of Muslims as a suspect community. Shain (2010) argues that the construction of Muslims as a suspect community shows a pre-emptive and increasingly coercive and punitive state approach to Muslim communities, which is justified by a ‘security’ discourse (p. 29). This allows the state to have minimal accountability for its bias against Muslims, claiming it is in the best interest of public safety. This pushes a narrative onto wider society that Muslims are dangerous and are to be feared, inherently creating a subconscious bias in the public mind. Adding to this argument, Spalek (2010) states that the branding of Muslims as ‘suspects’ has led to state surveillance and control (cited in Awan, 2012). Highlighting a correlation between state surveillance of Muslims and Muslims being categorised as suspicious.

As discussed earlier Prevent has many flaws, one being, it has a tendency to play into the idea of a Good Muslim and a Bad Muslim debate, further demonising the idea of a ‘suspect community’ (Mamdani 2004, cited in Shamim 2017, p.78). This then fosters a perception in the public mind that Muslims are to be feared, with some being deemed less threatening. For example, your next-door neighbour may be seen as acceptable, while a Muslim seen in an airport may raise suspicion. Lachman states, ‘The entire premise of the Prevent agenda is one where it demonises an entire community, to turn them into a suspect community’ (cited in Ragazzi, 2016, p.731). Further highlighting the role of policy and suspect community.

The way law enforcement treats the Muslim community emphasises that the community has been branded as suspicious. For example, Statistics show between September 2001 and March 2008 over 1500 people had been arrested under counter-terrorist legislation, only a third of these were charged, and one in eight ended in conviction (Home Office 2009, cited in Awan 2012, p.22), showing Muslim

individuals had been regularly targeted by counterterrorist police. Hillyard (1993) argued that police and community relations in the UK have been damaged since the first introduction of counter-terror laws (cited in Awan 2012, p.24). This identifies a correlation between state violence and poor community relations. The community does not wish to engage in the state if the state actively marginalises the community. Furthermore, Pantazis and Pemberton (2009) contend that high-profile police raids, arrests, and detention of 'Muslim terrorist' suspects have had a clear impact on the public consciousness (p. 661). Further showing that actions of the state can have a big impact on the public mind. This dissertation argues that Islamophobia is so prevalent within the public mind that it shapes how society views terrorism as a whole. As discussed previously, Prevent is viewed as both a product of and a contributor to Islamophobia. Here, Pantazis and Pemberton are showing that general society views the Muslim community as suspects, and therefore inherently treats the Muslim community as suspects. Additionally, in England and Wales, police officers carried out 302 percent more stop and search operations against Asians in 2002-2003 than in 2001-2002 (Bonino, 2012, p.18). Demonstrating a shift in police attitudes and treatment towards Asian individuals or those that fit the Muslim stereotype, post 9/11.

3.5 Summary

This chapter has discussed some of the reasons why society falsely believes that Muslim groups are overwhelmingly responsible for terrorism. This section looked at the role of the media and how this has facilitated and created a wave of terror within the public mind. This chapter spoke about how Muslim women specifically have been used as propaganda to promote anti-Islamic values, depicting them as oppressed, battered, stuck in an outdated system and in need of saving. This chapter discussed policy and the way that it can shape the public mind. This chapter discussed the way in which the Prevent policy has dictated the notion that Muslims have been branded as suspicious. This chapter also looked at other forms of policing agenda that demonstrate Muslims are unfairly stereotyped, such as the use of CCTV cameras and increases in stop and search statistics. This chapter has looked at the ways Muslims have been branded as a "suspect community" and how this occurred, through an array of factors such as treatment of the Muslim community by law enforcement.

Chapter 4: How Muslims Have Been Affected Since Being Stereotyped as Terrorists?

4.1 Overview

This chapter will discuss the impact that the 'all Muslims are terrorists' stereotype has had on society and, more importantly, the effect this has had on Muslims within their day-to-day lives. After 9/11 the implications for Muslims all over the world were dire, and society grouped Muslim men and women into stereotypes. For Muslim women, this construction mostly impacts their ability to wear religious clothing freely. Additionally, it has impacted the level of safety they feel in public spaces. For Muslim men, they have been constructed as problematic and branded as dangerous. As a result of this, non-Muslim groups in society have been led to believe they should fear Muslim men. For Muslim students, education is no longer a space of debate. Instead, it is problematic. Often Muslim students fear they no longer have freedom of speech and worry that engaging in political discussions or debates may lead to a referral to counterterrorist programmes.

4.2 Anti-Muslim Aggression

As briefly discussed in the literature review, anti-Muslim aggression already existed pre 9/11, the attacks in New York solidified these feelings. Just a few days prior to 9/11, the UN declared their formal recognition of Islamophobia, establishing anti-Muslim prejudice, discrimination, and hatred, placing this alongside other discriminatory phenomena, such as antisemitism (Allen, 2004, p.2). This event seems to have been forgotten when discussing the phenomena of Islamophobia. As stated, there is an overarching focus in literature that 9/11 acted as a catalyst for anti-Islamic sentiments. This however demonstrates that 9/11 did not create a hatred towards Islam; it legitimised it. As this dissertation will continue to argue, it is during the post 9/11 era that anti-Muslim feelings make their way into everyday life, shaping things such as policy and the media, which shapes the way society views terrorism. Hate crimes targeted at Muslim civilians post 9/11 was catastrophic. Allen (2004) discusses the post 9/11 attacks towards Muslims that had been reported. He states that in Britain an 18-year-old Muslim woman had been beaten by men with baseball bats in Slough purely due to the fact she is clearly a Muslim (p4). Ahmad (2004) states that in the days and weeks after September 11 over 1,000 bias incidents against Arabs, Muslims and South Asians were reported (p.1261). It is important to note that violence targeted at Muslims did not strictly just occur in the aftermath of 9/11. In 2011, 52 percent

(632) of hate crimes recorded by police forces in England and Wales were classed as hate crimes against Muslims (Copsey et al. 2013, p.7). As these are classed as official figures, it is important to note that there is a chance crimes were under-reported. The feelings of hatred towards Islam, however, does not just effect Muslims. Allen (2004) notes that since 9/11 a wave of distrust was created, which extended to any person who slightly resembled the Muslim stereotype. This resulted in attacks on Sikh men, due to their skin colour and beards (cited in Massey & Tatla, 2012). Both Muslim men and women, and, as stated, men and women who 'resembled' Muslims were exposed to high levels of violence post 9/11.

4.3 The Impact of Muslims Being Branded as a Suspect Community

The construction of Muslims as a suspect community has had negative consequences for Muslims, but also anyone perceived to be Muslim, anyone that resembles Islam, or looks similar to the Muslim stereotype. One key prime example of this is the killing of Jean Charles de Menezes. Jean Charles de Menezes was shot on the 22nd of July 2005, at Stockwell Tube station. Menezes was mistaken for Hussain Osman, a man who was suspected to be behind a failed suicide bomb attack (Bailey, 2008). This example demonstrates how anti-Muslim sentiment often groups together those who are brown skinned and 'Arab looking' into a very loose and inexact grouping. Menezes was perceived to fit the stereotype of a Muslim man, most likely due to subconscious anti-Muslim sentiments. Islamophobia is the fear of Islam, the fear of Muslims, or the fear of anyone who remotely resembles either. Additionally, in the immediate aftermath of 9/11 the majority of Americans incorrectly perceived Sikhs as Muslims. This is due to a false understanding of Muslims' appearance, which includes a beard and a turban (Goodstein & Lewin, 2001, cited in Ahluwalia & Pelletiere, 2010). The Muslim Council of Britain articulated concerns to the Home Affairs Committee on Terrorism and Community Relations that once a community is treated as a 'suspect' by the police 'the public are encouraged to do the same' (HAC 2005. Cited in Pantazis & Pemberton, 2009, p.660-661). This contributes to the notion that the construction of Muslims as suspects has dire consequences in day-to-day life.

Furthermore, when conducting research on the impact of being a 'suspect' on Muslims Hickman et al. (2012) found that Muslim individuals often avoid discussing politics, are careful when on the phone or browsing the internet and take caution to not mention al-Qaeda or terrorism (p.98). The construction of Muslims as a suspect community then in turn impacts the community itself. Ahmed (2017) argues the social impact on the communities associated with those terrorist groups can deteriorate inter-community relations (cited in Ylitalo-James, 2020, p. 48). As discussed, Muslims have been put into categories such as the 'good' versus the 'bad' Muslim. An example of 'good' Muslims are informants

who work for the government and an example of 'bad' Muslims would be those who symbolize terrorism and represent the threat of "home grown terrorism" (Maira 2009, p. 639). However, Muslims have also been categorised as 'moderate' Muslims. The categorisation calls for 'moderate' Muslims to be active in addressing the threat of domestic terrorism or radicalisation (Cherney & Murphy, 2016, p.160). This notion suggests that Muslims should be active within their community to counter violent extremism. This links back into the discussion of how counter-terrorism policy impacts Muslims. Prevent demonstrates the way in which Muslims can be categorised as 'good' or 'bad'. As a result of Muslims being a suspect community, Patel (2012) discusses a type of suspect profiling that focuses on 'brown bodies'. Patel (2012) argues that surveillance related to terror incidents singles out people of Middle Eastern, Arabic, South Asian and or of Muslim faith (cited in Acik and Pilkington, 2018, p. 20). Demonstrating that not only the Muslim community has been impacted, but also anyone perceived to fit the Muslim stereotype.

4.4 The Impact Policy has had on Muslim Individuals

As discussed already, Prevent Britain's counter-terrorism policy has had and still does have a great impact on Muslim lives. PVE was launched via a series of documents and toolkits aimed at supporting schools, colleges, universities, and other public bodies in the task of challenging 'extremist' behaviour (Shain, 2010, p.30). Prevent has led to Muslim students self-censoring in class discussions; it has encouraged surveillance, racial profiling, and suspicion within educational settings (Holmwood & Aitlhadj, 2022, cited in Poynting & Tufail, 2023). Innocent Muslim students are being accused of having an involvement in terrorist organisations, a 14-year-old schoolboy in London was suspected of being radicalized because he used the term 'L'ecoterrorisme' in a discussion about violence and the environment (Dodd 2015, cited in Saeed 2016 p.36). This example identifies the catastrophic implications that prevent has had on children in the classroom. It can be argued that to refer a 14-year-old to counter-terrorism support identifies a real problem within the system, and Saeed (2016) argues that mostly when Muslim students have been branded as 'radical students' it predominantly affects Muslim male students (p.94). However, statistics show that in the year ending March 2024, 2,729 individuals aged 11 to 15 were referred to Prevent. This was 40 percent of all referrals made that year (Gov. UK, 2024). This demonstrates that there is a clear correlation between this specific age group and the risk of radicalisation.

Furthermore, there are numerous experiences discussed in the press that identify an abuse of power within the system of Preventing Violent extremism. Two brothers, who were aged five and seven, were referred by their school to the police over fears of 'radicalization' when one had mentioned a toy gun

(Addley & Topping, 2017; Stein & Townsend, 2021 cited in Tufail & Poynting 2023). Both examples identify an abuse against power and clear discrimination of Muslims. Looking at Prevent in a different light, it can be argued that policy creates feelings of hostility that can in fact end up pushing young Muslims to radical ideologies. Abbas (2019) argues that British Muslims turn to the state with hopes that it will respond to the problems Muslims are facing, the state does not return the interest. Abbas then argues that this indicates institutionalised Islamophobia, which is a result of the failures of the 'War on Terror' and a result of the culture it has ensued (p402). This demonstrates the feelings of Muslims in the UK, as feeling failed by the British government. Counter-terrorism measures led individuals to perceive the threat of terrorism to be higher than it is. As Pantazis and Pemberton (2009) argue, one of the ironies of counter-terrorist measures is that it manufactures 'terror' (p 654). Individuals who work in the public sector are now made to be agents of the state, constantly looking for individuals at risk or susceptible to radicalisation. This creates a wave of terror. Individuals perceive the terror threat to be high, as they are being made to look out for signs of terrorism.

4.5 How Gender has Impacted Anti-Muslim Aggression

Gender plays an important role in the construction of Muslims as terrorists, specifically with Muslim women's clothing and the way it has been vilified. Research has shown that being visually identifiable as a Muslim is the most powerful predecessor to aggression towards Muslims. The hijab has been found to be the primary visual identifier (Allen & Nielson, 2002. Cited in Ghumman and Ryan, 2013, p. 675). Therefore, Muslim women have faced a number of brutal, racially motivated attacks post 9/11. Due to their clothing being vilified, they are at the forefront of anti-Muslim aggression. Within the two months following 9/11, there were more than 300 reported assaults against Muslims in the UK. The majority of these attacks were targeted at Muslim women as a result of them being identified as Muslim due to their hijab (Freedman, 2007, p. 30). Attacks on Muslim women have had a great impact on their livelihood. A study of the PTSD effects on Muslims after 9/11 found that a significantly larger proportion of women (86.3%) versus men (54.9%) had experienced hate crimes (Perry, 2014, p80). There is a strong notion that the veil is dangerous, and this is why Muslim women are targeted. In France, a right-wing member of Parliament went as far to argue that Muslim women could use their burqa to conceal a bomb (Posetti, 2007, cited in Perry, 2014, p83). This is a good example of the way in which Islamophobia seeps into society, here an individual with status is demonstrating a hatred of Islam by discussing the veil in a discriminatory manner. The right-wing individual is discussing anti-Islamic views in a context of power, discussing the veil in a negative light in parliament. This demonstrates a process of normalisation. It expresses to the public that their discriminatory opinions are valid. The impact of

gendered Islamophobia has led to women being forced to prioritize safety over expression of identity, meaning many women have questioned their choice to be covered (Perry, 2014, p.85).

4.6 The Ways in Which Muslim Men Have Been Othered

Scholars argue that all Muslims have gone through a process of othering. Scholars have noted that U.S. media accounts of terrorism employ linguistic strategies to ignore violence committed by “us” and rather focus on negative behaviour of “them” (Cainkar, 2004. Cited in Silva, 2017, p.140). This means that there is a discourse that suggests Muslims are separate from the rest of society; they are viewed as others, as different. In the UK Poole (2009) argues that the increased media focus on Muslim groups has established a ‘crisis of national identity’ whereby a narrative is developed, nationally, that excludes Muslims from identifications with Britishness (cited in Sian & Sayyid, 2012, p.230).

Muslim men specifically have been branded as suspects and targeted as a result of this. Muslim men are often said to be viewed through a problematic, media fuelled discourse that focuses on women’s safety or a risk to women’s safety (Fitzsimons, 2017). It is important for this dissertation to discuss othering as it demonstrates what the impact has been in the post 9/11 era. Fitzsimons (2017) argues that today’s most prevalent othering has narrowed somewhat towards an erroneous homogenised Muslim/Arab identity where simply being Muslim, in some ways, links a person to so-called Islamist extremism (p. 264). Kundnani (2015) argues that this is the dominant lens through which the West views Muslim populations and is the justification for counter-terrorism policies that undermine the human rights of tens of millions of people worldwide (cited in Fitzsimons, 2017, p.264). Linked to the concept of othering is the notion of the enemy within. Since the 7/7 bombers were British citizens, they had been labelled as home-grown extremists. When discussed within literature on terrorism and radicalisation and via the media, this led to these “radicalised” youths being referred to as “the enemy within” (Weinstein, 2008, cited in Lynch, 2013, p.243). The ‘enemy within’ narrative was an appeal to the public to eradicate and reveal those who are disloyal and going against the norm (Steans, 2008).

Although this dissertation has discussed the way in which Muslim men have been othered, Mirza (2013) argues that it is highly visible that it is the Muslim woman who symbolises the ‘barbaric Muslim other’ (p.97). This argument interlinks with the discussion of how gender has impacted anti-Muslim aggression, demonstrating that Muslim women have experienced a form of gendered Islamophobia. Furthering this discussion, Afshar (2013) argues that Muslim women in Europe have been otherized and punished for choosing to follow a specific dress code. Overall, Islamophobia is a general cultural

phenomenon that has led to Muslims being seen as racial others and has facilitated a security discourse in which Muslims are predicted to be a potential imminent threat to national security (Sheehi, 2018).

4.7 Summary

This chapter has discussed what the implications have been since Muslims have been categorised as a suspect community. This chapter has discussed the impact that policy has had on Muslims, with a focus on how it has impacted Muslims in an educational setting. This chapter has discussed how policy has had a negative impact on Muslims of all age groups. This chapter looked at the ways in which Islamophobia can be gendered, and how Muslim women are at the front of brutal anti-Muslim attacks due to being identifiable as a result of their religious clothing. Additionally, this chapter looked at the ways Muslim men have been othered, and what it means to be categorised as an 'other' in modern society. This chapter discussed the impact that this has had on Muslims and the impact this has had on individuals perceived to be Muslim as a result of stereotypes. Finally, this chapter discussed how the concept of othering has been applied to Muslim women.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

5.1 The Relevance of This Research

This chapter will discuss the overall conclusion of this dissertation. It will combine all the evidence demonstrated throughout. Since the terror attacks of 9/11 and the attacks that followed in Europe, assumptions about the Muslim youth in Europe became generalised. In the UK, Muslims regardless of age became a national security concern, the focus of state intervention and have had their loyalty to their country of residence questioned on numerous occasions (Lewis 2007; Humphrey 2009. Cited in Lynch 2013). However, anti-Muslim hate is still a pressing issue. Tell MAMA is a foundation that researches into Anti-Muslim hate and records these incidents. In 2024, they stated that they had received the highest number of anti-Muslim hate cases recorded in a single calendar year, with 6,313 cases recorded and of which they verified 5,837, this had a 165% increase since 2022 (Tell MAMA, 2025, p.22). This statistic is key as it demonstrates the need for this research and shows the prevalence of Islamophobia in society. Furthermore, evidence has shown how Islamophobia has framed society's perception of terrorism. A USA Today/Gallup poll of 1,007 Americans conducted in 2006 revealed that 39% of respondents said they felt at least some prejudice against Muslims (Abu Raiya et al. 2008, p.311). Whilst this can demonstrate that Islamophobia frames the public mind, and some civilians recognise that they have a bias against Muslims. It is important to note that the sample size for this poll is very small and therefore hard to generalise. This statistic, however, does demonstrate the relevance of this research as it shows civilians recognise a bias within themselves. It is also important to note the date of this study, as it was conducted just under 20 years ago. Therefore, opinions may change, but it does still demonstrate the impact that 9/11 had on civilians, as it was conducted shortly after 9/11.

5.2 Key Findings

As discussed throughout this dissertation, the media (mass and social) have played a crucial role in the ramping growth of Islamophobia. The media provide a platform for anti-Islamic/ anti-Muslim statements, with accusations and condemnations by political leaders, media commentators and a host of "preachers of hate" as well as hate speech and hate crimes (Esposito, 2019 p.22). Additionally, it can be argued that all forms of Western media are responsible for maintaining these ridiculous stereotypes of Muslims (Hussain & Rosenbaum, 2004). Ahmad et al. (2021) adds to this as they argue that the media instil fear in the public by discussing terrorism in a stereotypical framework and have little initiative to counter Islamophobia or discuss how and why it is an issue. Furthermore, Allen (2002) argues that certain images and stereotypes are now so deeply embedded and almost necessary to media coverage,

Islamophobia is almost a natural process (cited in Ameli et al. 2007, p. 14). Additionally, the role of the media links into the concept of how gender impacts Islamophobia. The Western mass media tends to construct an image of Muslim women using a discourse that depicts them as passive and victimised (Navarro, 2010, p. 110). All examples demonstrate how Islamophobia has framed the way terrorism is viewed and how the media has enabled this to occur.

There is significant evidence to show that counter-terrorism policy does have an overarching focus on Muslim communities. There is an overwhelming amount of Preventing violent extremism funding aimed at Muslim communities, even though there is no evidence from plots to date that show terrorists are more likely to emerge from 'dense' Muslim communities (Finney and Simpson 2009, cited in Thomas 2010, p.446). Additionally, Awan and Abbas (2015) conclude that institutional levels of Islamophobia have been demonstrated via policies that outwardly targeted Muslim communities more than any other religious group (p.17). This argument supports the overall argument of this dissertation: Islamophobia has become so prevalent in day-to-day society. As discussed throughout this dissertation, policy plays a large part in the construction of the Muslim terrorist stereotype and impacts Muslims directly.

The OSI stated that veiled Muslim women had suffered the highest levels of attack and discrimination in the aftermath of 9/11 demonstrating a link between victim and recognisability (Allen, 2015, p. 289). There is a distinct correlation identified between aggression being directed specifically at Muslims. In the context of Muslim men, they have been depicted as 'angry men with long beards' (Culcasi & Gokmen, 2011). Furthering this point, Shazhadi et al. (2018) conducted a study on feelings of Britishness amongst young Muslims and found that participants mentioned that having a beard often resulted in the attraction of unpleasant attention and occasional discrimination (p.614).

5.3 The Impact of Islamophobia on Muslims

This research project was important as it shed light on a current issue. Whilst Muslims themselves recognise this ever-growing issue of Islamophobia in modern society, with one study finding that 63 percent of Muslims stating they feel more victimised than other religious groups (Ipsos Mori, 2018. Cited in Gilks, 2020, p.25). Non-Muslims recognise the issue but at a lesser rate, with 58 percent of British adults believing that Islamophobia is a serious problem in contemporary British society (ComRes, 2019. Cited in Gilks, 2020, p.25). Demonstrating that whilst both Muslims and non-Muslims recognise Islamophobia as an issue, the rate of individuals that recognise this is not high enough for the scale of the problem. Moreover, after the 7/7 bombings in London, one study found that Muslims and non-

White Londoners reported disproportionately more stress than members of other faiths and White Londoners (Rubin et al. 2005, cited in Fahim Uddin, et al 2022 p.77).

5.4 Concluding Argument

As this dissertation has shown, due to an array of factors, Muslims have become biasedly associated with terrorism. Beydoun (2020) demonstrates this through policy, arguing that government radicalization discourse and programs almost entirely fixate on Islam and Muslims (p.121). Or whether that be as a result of the media, a key example of this is a study conducted by Khalaf et al. (2022) into the impact of Islamophobia on Muslim students found that students experienced some form of discrimination from a peer, teacher or the school as a whole and believed these experiences had been exacerbated by the media, as it often spreads false information about Islam. This also highlights the ways Muslims have individually been impacted by Islamophobia and the construction of the Muslim-terrorist stereotype. Additionally, one study found that just 12 minutes of exposure to terrorism-themed news sufficed to increase prejudice against Arabs in general (Das et al. 2009. Cited in West & Lloyd 2017, p.212). Emphasising the negative impact, the media has had on individuals in relation to the construction of this stereotype.

5.5 Strengths of the Research Project

In conclusion, this research project aimed to contribute to the understanding of the topic of Islamophobia. This dissertation has highlighted a correlation between Islamophobic attitudes in society and the way terrorism is perceived by society, but as this project did not conduct its own research, some statistics used may be outdated. This research project has demonstrated throughout the entirety of the dissertation the ways in which Islamophobia can shape the way terrorism is viewed by society and has highlighted how it is a pressing issue in today's society. Furthermore, throughout this dissertation, key themes were identified that link together Islamophobia and the way terrorism is perceived. These crucial themes were the role of the media, gender and how Islamophobia can be gendered, the implications and impact of policy and how Muslims have been othered. This dissertation suggests that counter-terrorism policy needs to be revisited. Policy should not have an overarching focus on Muslim communities as it currently seems to have. Policy should aim to counter all forms of violent extremism and not just be concerned with the threat of Islamic terrorism.

5.6 Recommendations for Future Research

Unfortunately, the word count restricted this research project and stopped the analysis of all related factors. This dissertation recognises more research needs to be conducted on this topic to understand in even more depth the ways in which Muslims have been impacted as a result of Islamophobia. Additionally, further research should be conducted to try to discover ways that Islamophobia can be reduced in society. This dissertation did not conduct its own research, so if one were to repeat this project, one may wish to conduct research that is not literature based. Additionally, this research project did not solely focus on England and Wales. In order to get a better understanding of Islamophobia and how it frames the way society views terrorism, it may be better to conduct research that solely focuses on one country. This would be useful because the research would focus more and be more precise.

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